

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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SIGNS OF A PUBLIC METHOD IN THE LANGUAGE OF THE MASS MEDIA

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Abstract. Journalism is derived from the Latin word publicus, which means social, public. The journalistic style is a style that reflects the political-ideological, socio-economic, cultural relations. Written and oral versions of the journalistic style. The main articles on important socio-political issues of life include feuilletons and pamphlets, appeals, declarations. The publicist must explain and prove the big issues of life with logical considerations, arguments and reflections, thereby influencing the will and emotions of the listener.

Key words: journalism, characters, methodology, style, genre, linguistic concept.

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Abstrakt. Jurnalistika lotincha publicus soʻzidan olingan boʻlib, ijtimoiy, ommaviy degan maʼnoni anglatadi. Publitsistik uslub siyosiy-mafkuraviy, ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, madaniy munosabatlarni oʻzida aks ettiruvchi uslubdir. Publitsistik uslubning yozma va ogʻzaki shakllari Hayotning muhim ijtimoiy-siyosiy muammolariga bagʻishlangan asosiy maqolalar jumlasiga felyeton va risolalar, murojaatlar, deklaratsiyalar kiradi. Publitsist hayotning katta masalalarini mantiqiy mulohazalar, dalillar va mulohazalar bilan tushuntirishi, isbotlashi, shu orqali tinglovchining irodasiga, his-tuygʻulariga taʼsir qilishi kerak.

Kalit soʻzlar: publitsistika, personajlar, metodologiya, uslub, janr, lingvistik tushuncha.

ПРИЗНАКИ ПУБЛИЧНОГО МЕТОДА В ЯЗЫКЕ СМИ

Абстрактный. Журналистика происходит от латинского слова publicus, что означает социальный, публичный. Публицистический стиль - это стиль, отражающий политико-идеологические, социально-экономические, культурные связи. Письменный и устный варианты публицистического стиля. К основным статьям по важным общественно-политическим вопросам жизни

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относятся фельетоны и брошюры, обращения, декларации. Публицист должен объяснять и доказывать большие вопросы жизни с помощью логических рассуждений, аргументов и размышлений, воздействуя тем самым на волю и эмоции слушателя.

Ключевые слова: публицистика, персонажи, методология, стиль, жанр, языковая концепция.

Introduction. The main function of the journalistic style is to persuade people by highlighting the most advanced ideas and opinions in society.

There are many different approaches to defining and interpreting the stylistic essence of the language of mass communication. Many researchers believe that there are two approaches to solving this problem: at first glance, mass communication is described as a phenomenon that manifests itself in a non-style way. It reflects all kinds of functional styles of literary language. In particular, M. N. Kojina described the mass dialogue as "an event rich in extraordinary diversity, and it is manifested in all functional ways." In mass communication, functional styles are not pure, but slightly modified.

This suggests that the characteristics of mass communication stem from the conditions, methods, and tasks associated with communication. This approach complicates the methodological analysis of a number of television and radio broadcasts. According to him, some programs do not have a clear methodological feature. Some experts believe that similar shows or broadcasts belong to different styles. For this reason, the methodological position of the journalistic style still remains unclear.

One of the existing concepts is the existence of an industry called journalistic style in the language of newspapers, radio and television. These methodological features have been interpreted differently by different researchers. Some researchers describe journalistic style as a collection of information about certain newspaper genres - interviews, correspondence, headlines, internal and external events, while others say that news is not typical of journalistic style.

Similarly, the genre of television interviews is also a contentious issue.

In the narrow sense, journalistic style is not just about vocabulary. The uniformity of the language of mass communication is determined by the goals, objectives, and conditions of the social sphere it serves. Journalism serves the

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political and ideological spheres of society. Initially, the main function of this method was the voluntariness of language. But today we see how important information is in society. In modern journalism, language performs two equal functions: informing and influencing. Therefore, in the functional methodology, special attention is paid to the journalistic style and the dichotomy of the factors that make up the journalistic and informational style. The style itself, more precisely, is studied as a method of mass communication.

The factors that make up this style are an advanced system of genres. Among them, language functions are also formed. Information genres provide information, analytical genres analyze a topic or event, and influence journalism.

Traditional functional methodology was formed at the time of the emergence of the system-structural direction in linguistics. That is why in all methodological textbooks they are based on the laws of systematics: the specific features of each functional method are considered in terms of the stages of the language system (lexical, morphological, syntactic, and for the phonetic level of speech). The style is to use language. A system of functional stylistics analyzes the use of language functions in them, while the study of texts within a particular style, the communicative stylistics analyzes discourse, the author's clear-cut communication, and texts within a communicative situation.

From the point of view of functional stylistics, it is especially important to identify and describe the general stylistic laws in individual texts, the methodological features of texts of different styles.

For example, if we look at the journalistic style in diachrony, we can distinguish between constant and variable features of this style. Constants are the means by which a journalistic style is specific to any period and distinguishes it from other stylistic differences in the expression of literary language. They include standard expression and consistent application, social evaluation, authorship, author position, ideology, and values.

In addition to methodological constants, journalism also has variable features. Variability is a characteristic feature of the journalistic style that has dominated a particular period of social life. Examples of the changing characteristics of modern journalism are satire, intertextuality, rhetoric, and puns. Variable features are determined by extralinguistic factors. Each period reveals new features.

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If we look at the journalistic text from the point of view of communicative methodology, its main features are based on a systematic block consisting of the addresser and the addressee.

These concepts form the basis of the *addresser - intention - text - addressee - text acceptance - influence - discursive analysis*.

Conclusion. In conclusion, the role of the media in the development of language is enormous. The media today is defining the state and characteristics of our modern language. In the science of language, this is reflected in the concept of "media language".

The existence of a specific language of the media is one of the general laws of the information age. Using the linguistic, social and cultural-historical memory of specific languages, this language is used in the creation of mass communication texts that have an interethnic character.

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